

EVALUATION OF EFFECT OF MANNITOL ON TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY ASSOCIATED WITH RAISE IN INTRACRANIAL PRESSURE

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Our study objectives include monitoring, diagnosis of Elevated ICP using noninvasive methods and its treatment and to establish mannitol as an effective treatment option for raised cerebral edema/ICP in TBI patients. **Methods:** We have conducted prospective observational study on 180 participants of TBI aged between 20-70 years who had increased ICP hospitalized in SICU and MICU departments of Malla Reddy Narayana Multispecialty Hospital, Suraram, Hyderabad, Telangana, India with required demographic information of patients like age, sex, relevant clinical data like GCS, CT and MRI scan reports for follow up of cases we collected information from MRD ward and analysed mannitol effects by non invasive methods like GCS, CT and MRI. **Results:** At the end of our study we found that TBI patients aged between 20–30 were more, male patients are more SDH cases were more and after mannitol therapy there was greater recovery rate with and has no evidence of edema/ICP in majority of patients. No mortality rate was found. **Conclusion:** By this study we want to conclude by stating that Mannitol being as an osmotic diuretic it showed beneficial effects on TBI patients without mortality more research should be conducted on mannitol therapy in management of ICP and bring more awareness in society about its potential life saving effects as osmotic diuretic.

Keywords: Mannitol, TBI, ICP, GCS, CT, MRI, EDH, SDH, SAH, DAI, Contusions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mannitol is an osmotic diuretic classified as a sugar alcohol which is derived from a sugar mannose .It facilitates the removal of water from tissues which includes the Brain and cerebrospinal fluid into interstitial fluid and plasma, this leads or helps in the cerebral edema, elevated intracranial pressure, and cerebrospinal fluid volume and pressure may be reduced. Mannitol also promote the diuresis, prevent and management of renal diagnostic aid. It is given by injection and through mouth and inhalation. It is available in the form of injectable solution, mannitol injectable solution by IV as single or several dose ^[1, 2] Mannitol, an isomer of sorbitol and a naturally occurring 6-carbon polyol, is C₆H₁₄O₆. This naturally occurring molecule

generated by marine algae, bacteria, plants, fresh mushrooms, and numerous fruits and vegetables. It is often used in the culinary and medicinal industries due to its particular functional properties[2]. It has also been synthesized by the fructose and glucose hydrogenation, as well as from biological substances. Mannitol, a sugar alcohol with a sweet Flavors, is used in food and medicine to conceal harsh Flavors. It's a white, odorless powder with 10%, 20%, and 500ml solutions [3]. It causes plasma volume expansions and supplies oxygen to the brain by reducing the thickness of the blood. It causes osmotic gradient across BBB as result water moves from brain parenchyma into the intravascular space leading decreased volume and thereby lowering of intracranial pressure [4].Until the osmotic gradient is reached between plasma and cells mannitol effect is delayed for 15-30min and the osmotic effect is initiated it remains up to the period ranging from 90 min to 6 hours or beyond based on the conditions of the TBI [5].

Dosage

Mannitol concentration ranges from 5% to 25% and among which concentrations of 20% and 25% are used for the management of raised intracranial pressure. Dosing ranges from 0.18 to 2.5g/kg and more beneficial effect is seen in increased ICP when the mannitol dose is between 0.5g to 1.5g/kg/dose [4].

2. METHODOLOGY

STUDY DESIGN & STUDY SITE:

A prospective observational study in six months period was carried out in 180 participants of traumatic brain injury who had increased intracranial pressure along with few different conditions of injury with or without comorbidities. The entire confidential data of participants or positive subjects of injuries was taken from Malla Reddy Narayana Multi-Specialty Hospital, Suraram, Hyderabad. The participant's data was collected from blocks like emergency units include surgical intensive care units, MICU etc.

APPROVAL OF IEC: Our research study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) and the number is MRMCWIEC/AP/199/2023.

SAMPLE SIZE:

Total 180 patients diagnosed with TBI aged between 20 – 70 years of males and females with CT scans, MRI scans, GCS score, hospitalized and the patients who are treated with mannitol are included in our study and those who are not hospitalized, below 20 years and pregnant women and the patients with incomplete record files are excluded from our study.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Age wise Calculation of TBI and their percentage

AGE (in years)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
20-30	50	27.77%
30-40	48	26.66%
40-50	42	23.33%
50-60	28	15.55%
60-70	12	6.66%

Table 2: Total Percentage of Male and Female

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	158	87.77%
Female	22	12.22%

Table 3: Gender wise calculation of TBI and their percentage

Type of TBI	Male Frequency	Male %	Female Frequency	Female %
EDH	27	15%	3	1.66%
SDH	38	21.11%	5	2.77%
SAH	30	16.66%	6	3.33%
DAI	29	16.11%	3	1.66%
contusion	34	18.88%	5	2.77%

Table 4: Different types of TBI and their percentage

Types of TBI	Frequency	Percentage
EDH	30	16.66%
SDH	43	23.88%
SAH	36	20%
DAI	32	17.77%
contusion	39	21.66%

Table 5: Mannitol Therapy in Nonsurgical and Surgical TBI patients

Mannitol Therapy	Frequency	Percentage
In Non surgical	130	72.22%
Surgical	50	27.77%

Table 6: Initial Stage of GCS out of 15

GCS	Frequency	Percentage
4	8	4.44%
5	12	6.66%
6	50	27.77%
7	30	16.66%
8	25	13.88%
9	43	23.88%
10	12	6.66%

Table 7: GCS out of 15 after 4 days of Mannitol

GCS after 4 days	Frequency	Percentage
8	45	25%
9	25	13.88%
10	50	27.77%
11	25	13.88%
12	35	19.44%

Table 8: Final GCS Results out of 15

GCS	Frequency	Percentage
11	10	5.55%
12	25	13.88%
13	45	25%
14	40	22.22%
15	60	33.33%

Table 9: Overview of Mannitol Therapy for TBI

Type of TBI	Frequency	Drug and Dose	Dosing Interval	Number of days
EDH	10	Mannitol 100ml	BD	2 – 3 days
	18		TID	3 – 11 days
	2		QID	1 day
SDH	15		BD	2 – 9 days
	20		TID	2– 3 weeks
	8		QID	1 – 5 days
SAH	24		BD	1 – 9 days
	10		TID	2 – 9 days
	2		QID	1 – 2 days
DAI	11		BD	7 – 11 days
	21		TID	3 – 5 days
	-		QID	-
Contusions	10		BD	5 – 7 days
	25		TID	5 – 9 days
	4		QID	1 – 2 days

Table 10: Mannitol therapy for TBI patients According to Dosing Interval

Mannitol dosing interval	Frequency	Percentage
BD	70	38.88%
TiD	94	52.22%
QiD	16	8.88%

Table 11: Overall Recovery Rate in TBI patients after Mannitol Treatment

Recovery Status	Frequency	Percentage
No evidence of edema	134	74.44%
Near to complete resolution of edema	46	25.55%

4. DISCUSSION

Our study focused on the role of mannitol as an osmotic diuretic in reducing ICP/Cerebral edema in various types of TBI patients. This study was conducted as a prospective observational study in 180 subjects who are hospitalized in SIC and MICU departments with TBI in Malla Reddy Narayana Multispecialty Hospital and for further follow up of cases we also gathered information from MRD. The subjects were categorized based on age starting from 20 years to 70 years in which the subjects between 20–30 age range were more with 27.77% followed by 30-40 years (26.66%), 40-50 years (23.33%), 50-60 years (15.55%) and 60-70 years (6.66%)

Overall percentage of male and female frequency were calculated and it was noticed that males were more with 87.77% when compared to female who were with 12.22%. Then we have analyzed TBI subjects according to gender wise in which SDH cases were more in males with 21.11% where as in females SDH and contusions were more with equal percentage of 2.77%.

We categorized different types of TBI and totally we observed five different types of TBI namely EDH, SDH, SAH, DAI and Contusions among them SDH were more with 23.88% (43) followed by Contusions, SAH, DAI and EDH with 21.66% (39), 20%(36), 17.77%(32) and 16.66%(30) respectively.

Then mannitol therapy was categorized according to non surgical and surgical and it was found that mannitol was indicated mostly in nonsurgical patients with 72.22% when compared to surgical patients (27.77%).

GCS was assessed initially and after mannitol therapy and in the initial stage we found GCS scores of 4-10 out of 15 and after 4 days of mannitol therapy GCS was improved with the range of 8 – 12 out of 15 and after complete course of mannitol treatment we found there was more increase in GCS with the range of 11-15 out of 15.

The mannitol therapy was categorized according to the dosing interval and duration in which mannitol 100 ml was administered mostly TID in 94 members and then BD in 70 subjects and QID in 16 subjects and the highest duration was of 2 days to 3 weeks, TID in SDH subjects. In DAI QID was not indicated.

Finally evaluation of Mannitol effect on TBI patients was done by comparing the edema/ICP before and after mannitol through scan reports and found that in initial stages there was large and thick sizes of hemorrhagic attenuations, Extra axial collections, SDH, aneurysms and multiple hemorrhagic foci and contusions and we took the scan reports after 48 hours of mannitol and we found decrease in sizes, volumes, densities and midline shift and in numbers and final reports were collected and analyzed and found that nearly 74.44% of subjects has no evidence of edema and nearly 25.55% has near to complete resolution of edema. No mortality was found.

5. CONCLUSION

Mannitol being as an osmotic diuretic it is showing beneficial effects of TBI according to literatures and in Hospital so we got interest to collect more information about mannitol effects and as a part of it we decided to do Project and discussed with our project guide and Critical Care Specialist. While evaluating the effects of mannitol we found practically that even in some patients with very low GCS mannitol has showed very good effect by improving their level of consciousness and we found that within 48 hours mannitol has decreased cerebral edema/ICP which we identified through scan reports by measuring sizes, thickness, volumes, densities and midline shift and we didn't find mortality with mannitol treatment during our project study. More research should be conducted on mannitol therapy in management of intracranial pressure and should bring more awareness in the society about its potential life saving effects as an osmotic diuretic.

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REFERENCES

1. Shawkat H, Westwood MM, Mortimer A, Mannitol: a review of its clinical uses. *Continuing Education in Anaesthesia Critical Care & Pain*. 2012; 12(2): 82–85, doi.org/10.1093/bjaceaccp/mkr063.
2. PanelJan Waskowski, Carmen A. Pfortmueller , Gabor Erdoes , Roman Buehlmann , Anna S. Messmer, Markus M. Luedi, Jürg Schmidli, Joerg C. Schefold A. Mannitol for the Prevention of Peri-Operative Acute Kidney Injury: A Systematic Review. 2019; 58(1):130-140. doi.org/10.1016/j.ejvs.2019.02.00
3. Heppel LA. A Pharmacological Study of Mannitol Hexanitrate. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*. 1941; 48(1):72-74. doi:10.3181/00379727-48-13224P
4. Peters NA, Farrell LB, Smith JP. Hyperosmolar Therapy for the Treatment of Cerebral Edema. *US Pharm*. 2018; 43(1): HS-8-HS-11
5. Liebert Ann M. The Use of Mannitol in Severe Head Injury. *Journal of Neurotrauma*. 1996;13(11): 705-709.